

The Influence of Substituents on the Stability of Schiff's Bases. Part I. Hydrolysis of Nitro- and Methoxy-benzylidene Anilines.

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Apart from the work of Reddelien and Danilof (*Ber.*, 1921, 54 [B], 3192) on the fission of a few aromatic keto-anils, little is known regarding the influence of substituents on the stability of Schiff's bases in general. Their results may be summarised in the general expression that the hydrolysis of anils by mineral acids in aqueous solution is facilitated by "positive" groups, such as NH_2 , NRR' , and retarded by "negative," such as NO_2 , COOH in the *para*-position to the nitrogen atom in the aniline residue. *Ortho*-substituents seem to exert steric hindrance. The cases examined by them, however, do not seem to be strictly comparable and no satisfactory attempt has been made to distinguish between the various factor that may influence the double bond in the system $>\text{C}=\text{N}-$.

For this reason, a systematic investigation of the derivatives of benzylidene aniline has been instituted with the object of differentiating between the following possible factors: (1) general polar effect; (2) induced polar effect; (3) effect of mass; (4) steric influence; (5) effect of conjugation, and (6) effect of constitutional changes.

In this communication, the hydrolysis of benzalaniline and the three nitro- and three methoxy-benzylidene anilines is described and the results are discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of the Anils.

Benzylidene aniline was prepared by mixing together equal quantities of benzaldehyde and aniline without the application of heat; colourless needles from methyl alcohol, m. p. 53° ; yield almost quantitative (Michælis, *Ber.*, 1891, 24, 750).

The nitro- and methoxy-benzylidene anilines were prepared in the usual way. The *m*-methoxy-benzylidene aniline, purified by repeated fractional distillation in vacuo, is a light yellow viscous liquid, b. p. 206-207° at 20 mm., (Found: C, 79.8; H, 6.3; N, 6.7. $C_{14}H_{11}NO$ requires C, 79.6; H, 6.2; N, 6.6 per cent.). The *o*-methoxy-benzylidene aniline distilling at 204-205° at 25 mm., solidified in a freezing mixture. It was further purified by crystallising from light petroleum in colourless needles, m. p. 33-34°, which is about 10° lower than the m. p. given by Noelting (*Ann. Chim. Phys.*, 1910, (viii), 19, 476). (Found: C, 79.7; H, 6.2; N, 6.7 per cent.). The *para* compound crystallises in colourless plates from light petroleum, m. p. 62.5-63.5° (Noelting, *loc. cit.*).

Hydrolysis of the Anils.

Equivalent quantities of the anils (1.2 g. of benzalaniline, 1.4 g. of a methoxy- and 1.5 g. of a nitro-derivative) were separately dissolved in a half-litre stoppered separating funnel in 300 c. c. of ligroin (b. p. 100-120°) and 75 c.c. of N/10 hydrochloric acid were then added to each. The funnels were shaken mechanically in a room the temperature of which remained at 16-18°. The liquids had been left in the room for a few hours previous to mixing so as to attain the temperature of the room. It was found that variations of temperature within this range did not materially affect the amount of anil hydrolysed. The shaking was carried out for varying periods of time, and at the end of each period the acid layer was quickly drawn off and diluted to 100 c.c. with water. Three 25 c.c. portions of the diluted solution were withdrawn, mixed with excess of dilute hydrochloric acid, cooled in ice, and titrated with N/5 sodium nitrite, using starch-iodide paper as indicator. The results of the second and third titrations, in the few cases in which they were not identical, did not differ by more than 0.2 c.c.; the mean was taken as the correct result. The sodium nitrite solution was standardised against a freshly made solution of pure aniline in hydrochloric acid. The results (from 140 experiments) are tabulated below.

Ligroin proved to be the most suitable of the common organic solvents. Blank experiments showed (a) that when a ligroin solution of an aldehyde, or its anil, is shaken with water, the aqueous solution after separation does not require more than one:

drop of the sodium nitrite solution to produce a blue colour on starch-iodide paper, and (b) that an aqueous solution of aniline hydrochloride when shaken with ligroin remains unaltered in strength. Further, the separation of the two layers, even after prolonged shaking, is almost instantaneous, no emulsion being formed. It is, therefore, reasonable to suppose that the quantitative data obtained by these experiments are strictly comparable.

Percentages of Anils Hydrolysed.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Time in hours.	ord. anil.	para nitro-	meta nitro-	ortho nitro-	para methoxy-	meta methoxy-	ortho methoxy-
1	58.4	32.8	35.7	21.2	81.8	54.0	78.8
2	75.2	47.4	51.1	32.8	87.6	69.3	82.5
4	80.8	65.7	67.2	55.4	88.3	84.7	84.7
8	85.4	69.3	70.0	62.8	88.3	84.7	84.7
18	90.5	75.2	75.2	65.7			
24	90.5	75.2	75.2	65.7			

Discussion of the Results.

A glance at the results shows that the reaction is reversible. Further, although from a polar point of view the substituent groups are opposite in character, the equilibrium points of the nitro- and methoxy-anils (maximum 75.2 per cent. for *p*- and *m*-nitro- and 88.3 per cent. for *p*-methoxy-) are distinctly lower than that of the parent substance. This result may be due to the effect of mass, but experiments have yet to be carried out with derivatives in which the substituents are of the same order of polarity but vary in mass.

The initial velocities of hydrolysis are in the order: methoxy-anils > parent substance > nitro-anils (except in the case of *m*-methoxy anil), which may be attributed primarily to the general polar influence of the substituent groups.

The initial velocities of hydrolysis of the isomerides, *para* and *meta*, are in the order: $m > p$ for the nitro-, and $p > m$ for the methoxy-anils. In the former case the difference, though small, is sufficiently above the range of experimental error. It is interesting to notice that the order of alternation is in agreement with the principles of induced alternate polarity as represented by the following formulae, oxygen being taken as the "key" atom:

(Compare Lapworth, Shoesmith, and others, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1392; 1923, 123, 2838; 1924, 125, 1312, 2278, on the hydrolysis and reduction of various substituted benzyl bromides).

The two nitro-derivatives, however, have the same equilibrium point, and even in the case of the two methoxy anils, the initial difference of 27.8 has been reduced to only 8.6 per cent. when equilibrium is reached. This would indicate that the influence of induced polarity is exerted *primarily* on the velocity.

In the case of *m*-methoxy anil, whose initial velocity of hydrolysis is lower than that of the parent substance, the general and the induced polarity are competing against each other. This result may, however, be attributed partly to this condition but not entirely, as it cannot be assumed that the effect of induced polarity is greater than the general polar effect. The question therefore must be left open until more cases of a similar nature have been examined.

The low initial velocity and equilibrium point of *o*-methoxy anil in comparison with the *para* compound may reasonably be attributed to steric influence, without neglecting to take into account the possible effect of conjugation as represented by the formula:

In the case of the two corresponding nitro-derivatives, however, the differences are much greater and in this connexion it should be mentioned that in addition to spatial influence there is the possibility of incipient structural alteration such as was demonstrated by Sachs and Kempf (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 2707. Compare also Ciamician and Silber, *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 2040).

Conclusion.

Dimroth and Zoeppritz (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 984) have shown that the formation and fission of anils should be regarded as additive reactions, *viz.*,

It follows, therefore, that any conclusion that may be drawn from this work might be equally applicable to additive reactions in general. Reference may be made here to the two general principles tentatively advanced by E. H. Ingold (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 469) in connexion with the Michael addition reaction, *viz.*,

- (1) "The primary effect of polar conditions is on the velocity of reversible additions."
- (2) "The primary effect of spatial conditions is on the equilibrium in reversible additions."

The results now obtained support the first principle as regards both general and induced polar conditions and the second only partially (see the figures for *p*- and *o*-methoxy-anil). Work to elucidate this point is in hand.

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